

Metaphorical connotation of Compound nouns in English**Baltabaeva Delfuza Baxtiyar qızı****A graduator of Master's degree at the department of English linguistics at Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh**

Abstract: In close connection with the indicated state of linguistics is the topic of this study, which is devoted to the description of compound nouns with metaphorical meaning in modern English. Both "composition" and "metaphor" are not new topics, they have a long tradition of study. However, the current level of development of linguistics, the emergence and development of new branches of knowledge in it make it possible to make from a combination of these seemingly traditional topics such an object of study that, in a new scientific coverage, or, in other words, within the framework of a new scientific paradigm, can give new important results.

Key words: nouns, compound nouns, descriptive method, metaphor, connotation, types of compound nouns.

Introduction: This work is devoted to the study of metaphorical meanings in compound words, in particular, in compound nouns formed according to the N + N model, in English, as well as to the determination of the specifics of the emergence of figurative (metaphorical) meanings in the process of creating compound words.

Before proceeding to the description of the process of development of metaphorical meanings, it is advisable to dwell on some issues related to a compound word in general, namely: to define a compound word, to show its role and place in the system of derivative words, to give a brief description of the formal and semantic features of compound words, to establish the differences between the semantics of compound words and the semantics of derivatives of other types, i.e. highlight the specific features of the compound word in general and the model under study, in particular.¹

Interlingual lexical equivalence is a concept that affects the vocabulary of any language. Within the framework of this concept, full equivalence, incomplete equivalence and non-equivalence are traditionally distinguished, which characterize the vocabulary of different languages. Despite the fact that the facts of lexical non-equivalence and incomplete equivalence are widely represented in languages, it is assumed that most words in different languages are equivalent, and they are based on an interlingual concept, that is, the denotative meanings of words in different languages completely coincide.²

The derived name is a new word, therefore its formal characteristics do not repeat in their totality those inherent in the original word. Being a new unit of nomination, the compound word also has new formal characteristics in comparison with its constituent components. The components in the composition of a compound word are deprived of those grammatical categories that are inherent in them as words in independent use. Thus, the morphological design of the plural inflection refers to the entire composite, and not to its components. Compare: *garden-houses*, and *gardens-houses*. Based on the fact that a compound word is also a new unit of nomination with new formal characteristics, it can be concluded that this feature is also shared by compound words.

Thus, the morphological design of the plural inflection refers to the entire composite, and not to its components. Compare: *garden-houses*, and *gardens-houses*. Based on the fact that

¹ Авеличев А.К. Метафора и контекст. Вестник МГУ, 1974, -С. 3.

² Авеличев А.К. Заметки о метафоре. Вестник МГУ, сер.Х, Филология, 1973, 181, с. 18-23.

a compound word is also a new unit of nomination with new formal characteristics, it can be concluded that this feature is also shared by compound words.³

Research methods: In conducting the research, a research design plays an important role in obtaining the data. It is the way information gained from the subjects. In this matter, the writer used descriptive qualitative study as the research design. They are definitional analysis, component analysis, the method of elementary statistical calculations.

Analysis and result. This study sought to investigate the use of the process of metaphorical connotation of compound nouns. From the result of the findings and discussion, it can be stated as follows. it expands the range of problems solved by derivatology and the theory of nomination. Having provided their theoretical apparatus for our study of new material - metaphorical compound words, word formation and onomasiology at the same time received a new impetus for further development based on the results obtained. ⁴ The paper provides a comparative analysis of metaphorical and non-metaphorical types of compound words, the role and place of metaphorical meanings in the system of meanings of a multi-valued compound noun, and also presents a possible classification of metaphorical meanings, shows the main ways of developing metaphorical meanings of derivatives. The significance of the study from a theoretical point of view is also due to the fact that when revealing a metaphorical meaning, the place of a metaphorical predicate is determined, which is present either in an explicit or implicit form, which makes it possible to establish on what basis the metaphorical meaning was formed compared to the literal. As criteria for selecting a compound word in this paper, we rely on two theoretical provisions, which, in our opinion, can form the basis for an adequate solution of this issue. Firstly, this is G. Paul's concept of isolation, which includes all aspects of composition: semantic, morphological, syntactic, phonetic. Thus, the defining features of compound words in this work are: 1) the semantic integrity (or isolation) of a compound word as an independent unit of nomination; 2) grammatical wholeness, namely: the absence of morphological categories in the components of a compound word that are inherent in their independent use; morphological design, for example, in the plural, refers to the entire compound word as a whole, and not to its components (morphological integral design); lack of expression of the syntactic connection between the components. We do not take into account the graphic integral design, therefore, among the analyzed items are separately designed units of the *cover girl type* - a "picture", a *pretty girl* whose portrait is obsessed with the cover of an illustrated magazine, etc.; *air potato* – клубниканың ботаникалық шаңарагына кириуши мийўе; *almond willow* – ботаникада, дәнели өсимликлер түрине криушия; *snow job* - амер. жарг. хийлегерлик пенен алдаў; жақсылап таярланган жалган, ақыллылық пенен өткерилген хийле. These criteria formed the basis for the definition of a compound word in our work.

Conclusion. Based on the data collected and analyzed from the observation, it can be concluded that the results of the work are summed up and conclusions are drawn about the role of the study of metaphorical composition in the development of some scientific disciplines.

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³ Азнаурова Э.С. Стилистический аспект номинации словом как единицей речи. В кн.: Языковая номинация (Виды наименований), М., 1977, с.86-128.

⁴ Бугулов Е.Н. Метафора как словообразовательное средство в английской научной терминологии. Киев: АН УССР, Ин-т теорет. физики, 1979. - 22 с.